

Susplace Final Event

“Exploring Places & Practices through Transformative Methods”

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Co-creating Models for RES Prosumerism in Portugal: Our Experience working with Living Labs

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Abstract

Co-learning, co-creation and co-production of knowledge are cornerstones of the PROSEU project [Prosumers for the Energy Union: Mainstreaming active participation of citizens in the energy transition]. Promoting an active participation of citizens in energy markets, institutions and decision-making seems essential to foster the transition to affordable, clean, low carbon energy. To do so in an inclusive and transparent way, a diversity of social actors (i.e. academia, industry, government, and civil society) should be included and play an active role in the process, instead of being passive objects of study. Living Labs (“living laboratories”) as environments for exploration, experimentation and evaluation of ideas, projects or products, hold the potential to gather multiple agents working on a common need in real-life contexts to co-create a solution that addresses local or community challenges. The involvement of multiple stakeholders in open innovation processes, contributing to knowledge exchange in new and imaginative ways, is a key approach in PROSEU’s research across nine European countries. In Portugal, two Living Labs were set up, where different actors interested in the energy transition exchange visions, expectations, drivers and barriers related to the production and self-consumption of energy from renewable energy sources (RES); and co-create, together, innovative solutions to mainstream the phenomenon of RES prosumerism in their region. In this session we will share our experience with these Living Labs, by presenting the first results of the (ongoing) experiences and lead participants through a creative brainstorming on the role Living Labs.